

CONVERSION OF HARDWOOD SAWDUST BIOMASS INTO BIOETHANOL

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ABSTRACT

The upward demand for renewable energy has generated interest in the conversion of lignocellulosic biomass into biofuels. This study researched on conversion of the abundant byproduct of the timber processes, which is hardwood sawdust biomass into bioethanol, because its richness in cellulose and hemicellulose. High Performance Liquid Chromatography and three key stages was utilized: pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, and fermentation. The sawdust was feed into a dilute acid pretreatment to break down the lignin and expose the cellulose and hemicellulose for enzymatic hydrolysis. Cellulase and hemicellulase enzymes were then employed to convert the cellulose and hemicellulose into fermentable sugars. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was used for fermenting these sugars into ethanol under optimized conditions. The filtration density, monitoring of the temperature of determining each yield of sample and monitoring the sugar brix on 6 hourly bases. The specific properties of this renewable energy source were vigorously explained in this study through the introductory concept in relating to the background of the study. The study used hardwood sawdust cellulose, SO₂, NaOH, crusher, oven, timer, filter etc. while the experimental method used was HPLC in achieving the purpose of the study. Discussions and results of this study was done through measurements of different variables required to meet the study purpose. The results demonstrated an efficient breakdown of hardwood sawdust, with significant yields of fermentable sugars and bioethanol. It indicates the significance of optimizing pretreatment and hydrolysis conditions to maximize bioethanol production. This research emphasizes the potential of hardwood sawdust as a viable feedstock for sustainable bioethanol production, contributing to the development of greener energy alternatives.

Keyword: Bioethanol, HPLC, hardwood sawdust biomass and Concentration.

INTRODUCTION

The application of sugar base and starchy based biomass as feedstock for biofuel production is at center stage due to the harm caused by fossil fuel. Energy sources (renewable and non-renewable) has been a major factor that determine economic progress of any society due to its role in providing basic needs such as transportation, electricity generation, domestic utilization etc (Balat and Balat, 2009). Bioethanol production is based on conventional approach such as simultaneous saccharification and fermentation, separate hydrolysis and fermentation, fermentation, saccharification etc., that are all scientific and technological applications (Adesuyi, 2013). This biomass comprises of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin that are often evaluated during the production process as opined by Ahmady *et al* (2014). These feedstocks are lignocellulose in properties due that enhances its overall characteristics for usage. As known, bioethanol is an oxygenated fuel that has a molecular formula of C₆H₁₂O₆. Traditionally, cellulose biomass like sawdust can be be applied as substrate for bioethanol manufacturing but requires scientific and technological application in breaking down the complex sugar through fermentation or saccharification (Brown, 2003). With the emission of greenhouse gases such as methane, CO₂ by fossil fuel, the need of seeking other options to this energy source is on the increase because of the harmful effect (Cheng, 1999).

Economic attraction of bioethanol can be achieved through effective production system that comprises of steps with cognizance on the kind of biomass being used in the production system

(Ahmady *et al.*, 2014). Bioethanol is classified according to its generation ie. first, second, third and fourth with suitable biomass for its production (Kadar,2012). In the manufacturing process, lignocellulose biomass like sawdust is less expensive, available and wholly accepted in achieving the product with high yield (Kadar, 2012). This product was discovered through the efforts of Henry Hunnel and S.E Serullas from Great Britain and France respectively (Ahmady *et al.*, 2014). With the unique properties of bioethanol, its benefits for human cannot be over emphasized.

America as a country as widely known continues to rely more on foreign oil due to lack of biomass materials in production of this product as opined by Energy Information Administration (2012) report. To decrease this dependent on foreign products such as crude oil which in itself continues to slow the economy, there is the need to encourage the production of biogas, biofuel and bioethanol to meet the energy demand of the nation (National Energy Education, 2014) report. The support for the increase use of biofuel does not simply hang on the need to reduced foreign oil dependent or the likely security risk that may follow but rather on the huge environmental benefits that accompany the usage of such home grown fuels. The application of biofuel are opposed to the conventional fossil fuel which always result in decrease in CO₂ emission, that is a major contributor to global warming and climate change (John, 2006). Bioethanol production is considered carbon neutral due to the growing process of the biomass that needs approximately the same amount of CO₂ during combustion (Adesuyi,2013). There are many conventional conversion methods of biomass to bioethanol of which high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is one of such approaches (Ahmady *et al.*,2014). The conversion process for biomass to bioethanol is explained in various figures in this thesis. Wood sawdust is obtained traditionally or scientifically from either hard or soft wood respectively that appears in powder form (Amin, 2009). It is scientifically noted that hard sawdust account for a higher yield due to its specific gravity (Adesuyi, 2014). The production process of bioethanol from biomass is explained in equation 1.

From the World Bank Watch Institute and Centre for Bioethanol Progress, asserts that Mexico corn meal price are up to 60%, they also report that Pakistan flour price has also increased due to high demand of bioethanol production from biomass. Also, China as major Asia's economy currently being faced with food price increases, especially in starchy based foods (Chum & Overand, 2001). The situation has been worst due to the factor of supply meeting up demand and taking into cognizance of economic concepts of inflation and recession as it is concerned with gross domestic product increase (Chum & Overand, 2001). From 1991 – 2001, global cellulose biomass like grain consumptions has increased tremendously due to growth in population rate and need of meeting global policy on emission of carbon by fossil fuel that is a huge source of greenhouse gas (Hodge *et al.*,2013). Experts has predicted how fossil fuel supply will be low in demand from 60 – 70 years from now (Duncan, 1999). Bioethanol is a vital component of organic compound with an overall beverage characteristic as reported by Duncan (1999). Wood and its residues, remains the highest biomass energy source currently (Johansson *et al.*,2008). Currently, researches are being targeted on algae and bacteria as potential biomass for bioethanol production (Ingram & Doran, 2005). Other biomass feedstock includes enzymes, yeast etc. Based on the source of biomass, biofuel is categorized into first, second, third and fourth generation respectively. According to Duncan (1999) Lignocelluloses biomass is grouped into various parts like wood residue, grasses, waste paper, agricultural residues and municipal solid waste etc. The crude oil global reserve is being depleted slowly and according to the World Bank (2019) report, 2010 estimate of global oil collection data for management of information showed that by 50 years

coming global fossil fuel reserve would be exhausted due to some factors like low production and its non-renewable characteristics. Bioenergy are renewable energy from energy crops and lignocellulosic residue, agricultural and wood based are experiencing global economic attraction for commercialization which will better the citizenry (World Bank, 2019) report. According to (Duncan, 1999) woody biomass are physically bigger and structurally stronger which make it heavier than the non-woody biomass. The woody biomass can be gotten all through the year, thereby eliminating long term storage (Duncan, 1999). The much lignin content characteristics increases the energy density of the biomass (Ingram & Doran, 2015), that possess zero ash content. Under weather condition, bioethanol is combustible, colorless that appear in fluid state (Ingram & Doran, 2015). It has a pleasant odour and familiar properties as it tastes suitably when diluted with water (Ingram & Doran, 2015). The uniqueness of bioethanol stem is majorly from the present of its OH group and the short nature of its chain of carbon (Anusiem,2013). Hydroxyl group of bioethanol participate in hydrogen bonding, making it less volatile and viscous polar organic compound of same molecular weight (Anusiem, 2013). According to Demirbas (2000) the polar characteristics of OH group make bioethanol to dissolve in many ionic compounds like Na, KOH, magnesium chloride, calcium chloride, ammonium chloride, ammonium bromide and sodium bromide etc. The advantage of biofuel application are enormous due its multi diversionary qualities that ranges from carbon neutrality and organic compounds availability. This study will no doubt be of benefit to man that is targeted in meeting the following objectives:

- To determine the filtration density of each sample,
- To monitor the temperature of determining each yield of sample.
- To monitor the sugar brix on 6 hourly basis.

One major problem facing this method of bioethanol production is the high cost of thermodynamic efficiency equipment involving operational system of the manufacturing process. Another obstacle being faced by this study is the difficult nature of the HPLC operational system in measuring viscosity of the fluid and other parameter such as volume and weight of each sample. The pretreatment process of HPLC is rigorous in nature and time involved is complex to determine due to inconsistency. Non availability of vital information on the HPLC production process is another challenge faced by the study. The process of measuring variables such as viscosity and concentration is cumbersome using the high liquid performance chromatography (HPLC) due to the dynamics of the HPLC efficiency. This study was faced with hurdles in the area of data collection due to the world energy crises being occasioned by global energy demands.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The materials used in achieving the aim and objectives of this study are: Sawdust substrate, sulphuric acid, sodium hydroxide, beaker, crusher, thermometer, oven, timer and strainer. Feedstock: - Hardwood sawdust was selected as the lignocellulosic biomass feedstock due to its high cellulose content and availability as a byproduct from the timber and furniture industries. Hardwood sawdust was collected from local sawmills, (the source of the hardwood sawdust was from Timber word Market Diobu Port Harcourt) dried, and sieved to ensure uniform particle size (0.5–2 mm). The Chemicals and Reagents that was utilized includes: Dilute acid: Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) which was utilized for the pretreatment of the lignocellulosic material. Enzymes: Commercial cellulase and hemicellulase enzyme mixtures were utilized for enzymatic hydrolysis. Yeast: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, a strain commonly used in industrial bioethanol production, was selected for fermentation. Buffers: Citrate buffer (pH 4.8) was used to maintain the pH during

enzymatic hydrolysis. The Analytical Tools that were used includes (1) High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) which was applied to quantify glucose concentration after hydrolysis and ethanol concentration after fermentation. Gas chromatography (GC) was used for the determination of the final bioethanol yield.

METHODOLOGY

The method applied to accomplish to research work is basically experimental method (Analytical Methods) as a Pretreatment of Hardwood Sawdust was the first step, which was followed by a size reduction, The collected hardwood sawdust was milled to a particle size of 0.5–2 mm to increase the surface area for effective enzymatic action. Drying: Sawdust was dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours to reduce moisture content and prepare the biomass for pretreatment. Dilute Acid Pretreatment. The dried sawdust was subjected to dilute acid pretreatment using 2% sulfuric acid (v/v) in a 1:10 (w/v) ratio of biomass to acid solution. Pretreatment was conducted at 120°C for 60 minutes in a high-pressure reactor to break down lignin and hemicellulose, making the cellulose more accessible for hydrolysis. The pretreated sawdust was washed with deionized water to remove residual acid and neutralized to a pH of 5–6 using calcium hydroxide. Enzymatic Hydrolysis, Enzyme Loading: A cellulase enzyme (20 FPU/g of cellulose) and hemicellulase enzyme mixture (50 U/g of hemicellulose) were added to the pretreated sawdust to convert cellulose and hemicellulose into fermentable sugars. Hydrolysis Conditions: Substrate concentration: 10% (w/v) pretreated sawdust. (1) Hydrolysis temperature: 50°C. (2) pH: Adjusted to 4.8 using citrate buffer. Time: 48 hours with continuous shaking at 150 rpm to ensure proper mixing and enzyme-substrate contact. Monitoring Sugar Release. The concentration of glucose and other fermentable sugars released during hydrolysis was measured at regular intervals using the DNS (3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid) method.

Fermentation

Inoculum Preparation, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was grown in a glucose-rich medium at 30°C for 24 hours to achieve a cell concentration of 1×10^7 cells/mL. Fermentation Setup. The hydrolyzed sawdust solution containing fermentable sugars was inoculated with 10% (v/v) of the yeast culture. Fermentation was carried out under anaerobic conditions at 30°C for 72 hours with periodic sampling. Co-Fermentation of Pentoses. In parallel experiments, engineered strains of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* capable of fermenting pentose sugars (such as xylose) were also tested to maximize ethanol yield from the hemicellulose fraction of the sawdust. Distillation and Bioethanol Recovery. The entire process was subjected to distillation in order to separation of Biomass: After the fermentation was done, the yeast biomass and residual solids were separated by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. Hence the distillation of the liquid fraction was performed in order to distilled and recover ethanol at 78.37°C under normal atmospheric pressure. Ethanol purity was enhanced using fractional distillation, with the final product concentrated to greater than 95% ethanol.

Analytical Methods

Glucose Concentration. The concentration of glucose and other fermentable sugars released during enzymatic hydrolysis was quantified using HPLC equipped with a refractive index detector. Ethanol Yield- The ethanol concentration in the fermentation broth was measured using GC. The bioethanol yield was expressed as grams of ethanol per liter of fermentation broth. Process

Efficiency. Ethanol yield was calculated based on the initial glucose content and the theoretical maximum ethanol yield, as follows:

$$\text{Ethanol Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Actual ethanol produced (g)}}{\{\text{Theoretical ethanol yield (g)}\}} \times 100$$

Process Optimization. Optimization of Hydrolysis Parameters. The enzyme loading, hydrolysis temperature, and pH were optimized by conducting a series of experiments to determine the conditions that produced the highest glucose yield. Fermentation Kinetics. Fermentation conditions, including inoculum concentration, temperature, and time, were adjusted to maximize ethanol production. The production procedure adopted for this study is the High Performed Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) that involves the following steps:

- I. Sourcing of the biomass; the sawdust was obtained from a sawmill in Egboam-Ogbogolo, Ahoada-West L.G.A of Rivers State. Nigeria.
- II. Physical preparation: 130g of sawdust was dried, crushed and sieved. The essence of the drying was to remove moisture and crushing was done for easy sieving. After these physical preparation processes, experimental approach using HPLC was employed so as to achieve the purpose and objectives of the study.

The sawdust was pretreated applying sulphuric acid. The feedstock was the fermented to degrade the sugar content in the sawdust; the mass of the sugar produced and that unrecovered were measured using Aminex-HPX-97H. After these processes, the p^h of the mixture was 2.4, but as a result of this low p^h , NaOH was prepared and added to boost the p^h to 3.1. The mixture was filtered which was then followed by the HPLC analysis. The achievement using the HPLC method involves conversion of sugar in the fermentation liquor and the total concentration of the reducing sugar ie., sugar produced and sugar unrecovered. The mixture was put in three different samples in which the weight and volume was measured to know filtration density. This method involves the concentration of bioethanol in the fermentation liquor and the total concentration of total reducing sugar in hydrate. The produced sugar was 17.5g, while the unrecovered sugar was 6.8g. Applying mathematical formula.

$$X\% = \frac{C_1}{C_2 \times 0.51} \times 100 \tag{2.}$$

Where

C_1 is Concentration of the bioethanol in the fermentation liquor and C_2 is Concentration of total reducing sugar in the carbohydrate and %X is the liquid fraction.

Economic Analysis. The cost-effectiveness of the overall process was evaluated, focusing on enzyme consumption, energy input, and ethanol yield.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The weight and volume were measured in other to determine the density

Mass (g)	Vol.(ml)	Density(g/ml)
13.31	19.00	0.705
19.92	20.00	0.996
21.60	21.00	1.029

The temperature of achieving the yield was monitored and presented in Table 2

Table 2: Bioethanol yield and monitored temperature

Bioethanol yield (%v/v)	Temperature (°C)
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3.00	10
8.00	20
15.0	30

The temperature of the filtrate density was also monitored and presented in Table 3.

Fig 1: Plot of Bioethanol yield against Temperature

Table 3: Filtration density and monitored temperature

Filtrate Density (g/ml)	Temperature (°C)
0.705	10
0.996	20
1.029	30

Fig 2: Plot of Filtrate density against temperature

The bioethanol yield and density of the filtrate are presented in Table 4

Table 4: The bioethanol yield and filtrate density

Bioethanol yield (%v/v)	Filtrate density(g/ml)
2.00	1.0400
10.0	1.0377
20.0	0.9712

Fig 3: Plot of Bioethanol yield against Filtrate Density

The sugar brix was monitored in 6 hourly basis which is then presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Time taken for fermentation and sugar brix

Time (hrs)	Sugar Brix
0	21.7
6	24.3
12	23.4
18	27
24	25.2

Fig 4: Plot of Time against sugar brix

DISCUSSIONS

From the plots in Fig. 1 the linear shape and zig-zag shape of the graph in Figure 2 showed the efficient nature of the production process using HPLC method while Fig.3 was stable in movement due to upgrading of the concentration of the mixture. The bioethanol yield and density of the filtrate were monitored through the temperature. The plot in Fig.3 also detailed the effectiveness of the HPLC in the production process showing stability of the production movement. The time needed for this process was 25hrs. Each yield of the sample of each component was noticed to be of different volume with its concentration been observed though the graphical representation. The graphs were plotted in ascertaining the economic value in quantity that can predict the supply when comparing with demand.

CONCLUSION

This study through the experimental approach has revealed the economic significant of bioethanol as source of energy foe human application industrially and domestically. The revelation of this study has given the economic and thermodynamic advantages of this oxygenated fuel as an option for fossil fuel that has been threatening human lives through emission of toxic substances. The experimental results obtained in this study showed that the yield of the bioethanol increases with the temperature as monitored. The results showed that developing nations like Nigeria, development of modern infrastructure will be achieved economically through the production of this product. The specific characteristics of this fuel is another advantage of this society. The conversion of hardwood sawdust biomass into bioethanol using enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation provides a sustainable method for biofuel production. By optimizing pretreatment, hydrolysis, and fermentation parameters, this study aims to develop an efficient process that can be scaled for industrial bioethanol production.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has made the following recommendations:

- ✓ The need of building a bioethanol refining plant by government and private operator.

- ✓ Proposing laws for regulating the production of bioethanol that will lead to setting up of regulatory agency.
- ✓ Formulating policies on marketing strategies of the product through effective monitoring

REFERENCES

- Ademark, P., Varga, A., Medre, J. and Stalbrand, H. (1998). Softwood hemicelluloses – degrading enzymes from *asperillus niger*. Purification and properties of a beta-mannaguase. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 64, 188-209.
- Adesuyi, A .O. (2013). Economic Impact of Biofuel in contemporary world: Important and concept. Heimann Publishing, Ibadan. Nigeria
- Ahmady, N., Sahar, K & Ashraf, K (2014). Bioethanol production from lignocellulosic feedstock based on Enzymatic Hydrolysis: Current Status and Recent Developments. *Journal for Asian Network for Scientific Information*. 13(1):1-12
- Ahmady, N., Sahar, K & Ashraf, K (2014). Bioethanol production from lignocellulosic feedstock based on Enzymatic Hydrolysis: Current Status and Recent Developments. *Journal for Asian Network for Scientific Information*. 13(1):1-12
- Ali, M.N., Mohammed, M.K. and Mohiudin, M. (2011). Bioethanol fuel production through microbial extracellular enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation from renewable agro base cellulosic waste. *International Journal of Pharma and Biosciences*, 2(2), 321 – 331.
- Amin, S (2009). Review on Biofuel oil and gas production from microalgae. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 50(7), 1834-1840
- Anusiem, C.T. (2013). Principles of General chemistry. Versatile Publiershers, Vol.2, pp. 47 – 48.
- Balat, M and Balat, H (2009). Recent trend in global production and utilization of biofuel. *Applied Energy*, 8(3),654-660
- Barley, E.J. and Ollis, F.D. (2009). Biochemical Engineering Fundamental, 2nd edition, pp. 39. McGraw Hill Publishers, Arizona United Sate of America.
- Blasig, J.D., Holtzapple, M.T., Dale, B.E. and Engler, C.R. (2002). Volatile sulphuric acid fermentation of ammonia fibre explosion (AFEX) treated bagase and newspaper by rumen microorganism CIA world faetbook (2005) cited 2010 August, 28. Retrieved from <http://nationmaster.com/graph/energy>.
- Brown, A.O. (2008). Biomass potentials in 21st Century: Issues and Concepts. *Journal of Applied Energy*, 86(11), 2273-2282
- Brown, A.O. (2008). Biomass potentials in 21st Century: Issues and Concepts. *Journal of Applied Energy*, 86(11), 2273-2282
- Cara, D., Ruiz, E., Ballesteros, I., Negro, M.J. and Castro, E. (2006). Enhance enzymatic hydrolysis of live tree wood by steam explosion and alkaline peroxide delignification. *Process Biochemistry Journal*, 31(3), 413 – 421.
- Celesi, B., Dunker, J.I. and Ramsay, W. (2000). Household energy and the poor in the third world. Resources for the future, Washington: RFF Press.
- Chang, V.S. (1999). Lime pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass (Ph.D Thesis, Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas, U.S.A.).
- Chang, V.S., Hotzapple, T.M. and Burr, B. (2000). Fundamental factors affecting biomass enzymatic reactivity. *Applied Biochemistry Biotechnology*, 73-78(1-7), 6-34.

- Cheng, K.K., G, J.R., Zhang, J.A., Ling.,H.Z., Zhou, Y.J., Yang, J.M (2007). Fermentation of pretreated sugar cane bagasse hemicellulose hydrolase to ethanol by *pachysolentannophilus*. *Biotechnology Journal*, 29(7), 1051-1055
- Cheng, V.S & Holtzapple, A (2018). Fundamental factors affecting biomass activities. *Applied Biotechnological Journal*, 84-86; 5-7
- Choi, G.W., Moon, S.K., Kang, H.W., Min, J & Chung, B.W(2009). Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation of sludge containing cassava for batch and repeated batch production of bioethanol by *saccharomyces cerevisiae*. CHF Y0321. *Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology*, 84(4), 547-553
- Chum, H.L. and Overend, R.P. (2001). Biomass and renewable fuels. *Fuel process technology Journal*, 71, 186 – 193.
- Colins (2009). Economic Advantage of Biomass. Multi Publishing Company, New York. United State.
- Conde-Mejia, C., Jimenez-Gutierrez, A. & El-Halwagi, M (2012). A comparison of pretreatment methods for bioethanol production from lignocellulosic materials. *Process safety and Environmental Protection*, 90(30), 189 -209
- Demirbas, A. (2009). Biofuel securing the planet's future energy needs. *Energy conversion and management*, 50(9), 2239-2249
- Doberman, A and Fairhurst, H.J (2002). Combustion of Biomass and its effects. *African Journal of Biotechnology Research*, 7(13), 38010-4101.
- Drakenberg, T.O. and Tjerneld, M.Y. (2008). Soft and Hardwood hemicelluloses-degrading enzymes from *Aspergillus niger*: Publication and Properties of a better of a beta mannanase. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 60, 189-200.
- Drakenberg, T.O. and Tjerneld, M.Y. (2008). Soft and Hardwood hemicelluloses-degrading enzymes from *Aspergillus niger*: Publication and Properties of a better of a beta mannanase. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 60, 189-200.
- Duncan, R. C (1999). Encircling the peak of world oil production. *Natural Resources Research*. 8 (3), 219-232
- Food and Agricultural Organism (2010). A potential renewable energy development and utilization of biomass energy: cited 2010 August, 27. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/docrop/0047E/E447oeonhtml>.
- Harris, E.E., Beglinger, O.F., Hajny, T.B. (2005). Hydrolysis of wood: Treatment with sulphuric acid in a stationar digester. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 36(2), 11-14.
- Hodge, D. B., Karim, M. N., Mohagheghi, A., Schell, D. J., Baker, J. O., & McMillan, J. D. (2013). Scale-up of high solids enzymatic cellulose saccharification from shake flasks to stirred tank reactors. The 26th Biotechnology Symposium for Fuels and Chemicals. May 1-4. Denver. CO.
- Ikenyiri, P.N. & Oghu, C, Y(2016). Comparative study on the Behaviour of Biomass adsorbent used in Environmental applications: Oil and Gas industrial effluent. *Nigeria Journal of Oil and Gas Technology*
- Ingram, L.O. and Doran, B.J. (2015). Conversion of cellulosic materials to ethanol. *FEMS Microbiology Review Journal*, 16, 233 – 238.
- Johansson, E. and Ljunggen, S. (2004). Kinetics of biomass reaction during photosynthesis delignation, *Journal of biotechnology and Genetic Engineering*, 7(1), 42 – 44.
- Kadar, Z (2012). Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) of industrial waste for the manufacturing of bioethanol. *Industrial Crops and Product Journal*, 31(4), 139 – 144.

- Klemn, D., Philipp, B., Heinze, U. and Wagenknecht, W. (2009). Comprehensive cellulose chemistry. Functionalization of cellulose (vol. 2, ed). Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH.
- Kryzanowski, T. (2008). From wood waste t-ethanol fuel, cited 2007 January, 25. Available from <http://www.forest.com>.
- Mahmudi, H., Flynn, J.P., Kazi, F.K. and Thomas, F. (2006). Biomass conversion procedures. *Applied biochemistry and technology Journal*. 91(2), 38-40.
- Martin, C., Negro, J.M., Alonsel, M. and Salz, R. (2008). Enzymatic hydrolysis of lignocelluloses biomass from onopordum nervosum: *Biotechnology and Bioengineering Journal*, 32(7), 341 – 344.
- Momo, H. (2007). Wood conversion to energy 1: the potentials and constrains of wood energy utilization in Africa. *Nigerian Journal of Renewable Energy*, 7(2-3), 132-138.
- Neely, N., Busto, D.M. and Miller, A.M. (2001). Factors affecting the pretreatment of biomass with gaseous ozone. *Biotechnology and Bioengineering Journal*, 25(2), 48-54.
- Nguyen, Q. A., Tucker, M., Keller, F., & Eddy, F. (2000). Two-stage dilute acid pretreatment of softwoods. *Applied Biochemistry. Biotechnology Journal*. 84-86, 561-576.
- Nidetzky, B., Steiner, W., Hayn, M., & Claeysens. (1994). Cellulose hydrolysis by the cellulases from *Trichoderma reesei*: a new model for synergistic interaction. *Biochemistry Journal*. 298, 3705-10.
- Nmegbu, G (2016). Lecture note on Renewable and non-renewable Energy, 2015/2016 Masters Degree Class, Department of Chemical/Petrochemical Engineering, Rivers State University. Port Harcourt.
- Wami, E.N (2010): Renewable and non-renewable Energy, Final Year Student Lecture, Department of Chemical/Petrochemical Engineering, Rivers State University. Pott Harcourt.
- Wan, Z.C and Li, C.H (2011). Starchy biomass Application in Bioethanol Production, *Journal of Biotechnology Application*, 59 (21), 321- 328.
- World Bank 2019 Annual Report on Energy Index Available on www.worldbank.com/annualreportonenergyusaged